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A manifold on the real commutative Banach algebra $C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R})$ that cannot be embedded in the finite-dimensional Euclidean space $C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R}^n)$

Hiroki Yagisita (Kyoto Sangyo University)

Abstract:

$C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R})$ and $\mathbb{R}^2 (= C(\{0, 1\}; \mathbb{R}))$ are simple examples of a real commutative Banach algebra. $C([0, 1]; \mathbb{C})$ and $\mathbb{C}^2 (= C(\{0, 1\}; \mathbb{C}))$ are simple examples of a commutative C^* -algebra. Here, we consider $C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R})$, which is the set of all real-valued continuous functions on the bounded closed interval $[0, 1]$. The interval is a contractible compact Hausdorff space. The direct product space $(C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R}))^n (= C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R}^n))$ is a real Banach space and a free $C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R})$ -module. A C^1 -mapping from an open set of $C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R}^n)$ to $C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R})$ is said to be $C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R})$ -smooth, if its Frechet derivatives are $C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R})$ -linear. Then, we can define a concept of an n -dimensional smooth $C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R})$ -manifold.

In this memo, we see existence of a connected metrizable 1-dimensional smooth $C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R})$ -manifold that cannot be embedded in $C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R}^n)$. In Section 1, as a primitive observation, we see that embeddability in the Cartesian space $C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R}^n)$ as a smooth $C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R})$ -submanifold implies existence of an analog of a bump function. Then, in Section 2, we construct an example where no such analog exists.

Keywords:

Serre-Swan theorem, complex vector bundle, locally trivial fiber space, partition of unity, Gelfand representation, von Neumann algebra, Radon measure, vector sheaf.

1 Primitive obstruction

Here, we make a primitive observation about a bump function and a separation function.

Proposition 1 (Embedding condition) :

Let M be a $C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R})$ -smooth manifold. Suppose that there exist $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and an embedding of M in $C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R}^n)$ as a smooth $C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R})$ -submanifold. Then, the followings hold.

(1) Let U be an open set of M . Let $a \in U$. Then, there exist open sets V and W of M and a $C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R})$ -smooth mapping f from M to $C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R})$ such that the followings hold.

$$a \in W, \quad \overline{W} \subset V, \quad \overline{V} \subset U$$

hold. For any $x \in M$ and $t \in [0, 1]$,

$$0 \leq (f(x))(t) \leq 1$$

holds. For any $y \in W$ and $t \in [0, 1]$,

$$(f(y))(t) = 1$$

holds. Let

$$\text{f.support}(f) := \overline{\{z \in M \mid \forall t \in [0, 1] : (f(z))(t) \neq 0\}}.$$

Then,

$$\text{f.support}(f) \subset V$$

holds.

(2) Let $a, b \in M$ and $a \neq b$. Then, there exist a $C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R})$ -smooth mapping f from M to $C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R})$ and $t_0 \in [0, 1]$ such that

$$(f(a))(t_0) \neq (f(b))(t_0)$$

holds.

Remark : In general,

$$\text{f.support}(f) \subset \text{supp}(f)$$

holds. Usually,

$$\text{f.support}(f) \neq \text{supp}(f)$$

holds.

Proof : (1) Let ρ be a usual bump C^∞ -function at 0 on \mathbb{R}^n . Let ε be a small positive number. Then, as we put

$$(f(x))(t) := \rho\left(\frac{(x-a)(t)}{\varepsilon}\right)$$

for $x \in M (\subset C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R}^n))$ and $t \in [0, 1]$, it follows.

(2) Let $U := M \setminus \{b\}$. Then, from (1), it follows. ■

2 Simple example

For convenience of description, we consider $[-1, +1]$ instead of $[0, 1]$.

Theorem 2 (Strange cylinder) :

There exists a connected metrizable 1-dimensional $C([-1, +1]; \mathbb{R})$ -smooth manifold M such that for any $n \in \mathbb{N}$, there exists no embedding of M in $C([-1, +1]; \mathbb{R}^n)$ as a smooth $C([-1, +1]; \mathbb{R})$ -submanifold.

Proof : We define an equivalence relation \sim of $C([-1, +1]; \mathbb{R})$ as follows. Let $(x, y) \in (C([-1, +1]; \mathbb{R}))^2$. Then, $x \sim y$ holds, if and only if there exists $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that for any $t \in [-1, +1]$,

$$y(t) = x(t) + nt$$

holds. So, let

$$M := (C([-1, +1]; \mathbb{R})) / \sim .$$

Let

$$a(t) := \begin{cases} 0 & (-1 \leq t \leq 0), \\ t & (0 \leq t \leq +1). \end{cases}$$

Then, $0 \not\sim a$ holds. That is, $[a] \neq [0]$ holds. Now, we show that there exists no bump function for $([a], M \setminus \{[0]\})$. To that end, we show that no $C([-1, +1]; \mathbb{R})$ -smooth function on M separates $[0]$ and $[a]$. That is, we show that for any $C([-1, +1]; \mathbb{R})$ -smooth mapping f from M to $C([-1, +1]; \mathbb{R})$, $f([0]) = f([a])$ holds. Let f be a $C([-1, +1]; \mathbb{R})$ -smooth map from M to $C([-1, +1]; \mathbb{R})$. Let

$$g_s := (1-s)0 + sa \quad (s \in [0, 1]).$$

Then, for any $s_1, s_2 \in [0, 1]$ and $t \in [-1, 0]$,

$$g_{s_1}(t) = g_{s_2}(t)$$

holds. Hence, because f is $C([-1, +1]; \mathbb{R})$ -smooth, for any $t \in [-1, 0]$, the map $s \in [0, 1] \mapsto (f[g_s])(t) \in \mathbb{R}$ is locally constant and, so,

$$(f([0]))(t) = (f([g_0]))(t) = (f([g_1]))(t) = (f([a]))(t)$$

holds. On the other hand, let

$$h_s := (1 - s)t + sa \quad (s \in [0, 1]).$$

Then, for any $s_1, s_2 \in [0, 1]$ and $t \in [0, +1]$,

$$h_{s_1}(t) = h_{s_2}(t)$$

holds. Hence, in virtue of

$$0 \sim t,$$

for any $t \in [0, +1]$,

$$(f([0]))(t) = (f([t]))(t) = (f([h_0]))(t) = (f([h_1]))(t) = (f([a]))(t)$$

holds. Therefore,

$$f([0]) = f([a])$$

holds. That is, no $C([-1, +1]; \mathbb{R})$ -smooth function on M separates $[0]$ and $[a]$. So, there exists no bump function for $([a], M \setminus \{[0]\})$. ■

Problem 3 : We define an equivalence relation \sim of M as follows. Let $([x], [y]) \in M^2$. Then, $[x] \sim [y]$ holds, if and only if there exists $m \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that

$$[y] = [x] + m[a]$$

holds. So, let

$$N := M / \sim.$$

Then, do there exist $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and an embedding of N in $C([-1, +1]; \mathbb{R}^k)$ as a smooth $C([-1, +1]; \mathbb{R})$ -submanifold ?

Comment : Kasuya proposed a candidate for a compact \mathbb{C}^2 -manifold N such that for any \mathbb{C} -manifolds M_1 and M_2 , N can not be embedded in $M_1 \times M_2$ as a \mathbb{C}^2 -manifold. The construction of our example was inspired by this proposal. —

Problem 4 : $L^\infty([0, 1]; \mathbb{C})$ is a commutative von Neumann algebra. Consider a $L^\infty([0, 1]; \mathbb{R})$ -manifold and a $L^\infty([0, 1]; \mathbb{C})$ -manifold. —

Oral :

If there is not much previous research, it will be either

Case 1: It has not been considered seriously.

or

Case 2: It is difficult to find related interesting problems. Or, even if you find a problem, it is difficult to get even a “partial result”.

By the way, manifolds on a (real or complex) commutative Banach algebra are very natural objects. Nevertheless, even an ordinary mathematician like me can get some “slight partial results” with just a few thoughts, and is likely to hit the case 1.

Now, it is great to create a novel breakthrough for a subject that has been studied extensively, but this is difficult. If you are a mediocre mathematician like me, you will likely be able to do a much better study on a subject that has not yet been considered.

But, there is one problem here. Because the research field has not been established, even if a result is obtained, there are not many people who immediately evaluate it. Therefore, it is not recommended that people who want to acquire academic posts in the future do their main research. To put it the other way around, it is highly recommended for permanent employees.

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